

Design And Fabrication of a Double Wishbone Suspension System for E – Vehicle

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Abstract:

The best suspension setup is a double wishbone design. Its design allows it to function on a broader range of terrain. Four-wheelers typically use this kind of suspension. In two-wheelers, the double wishbone suspension setup can also be employed with a modified design that is tailored to the vehicle's performance. By replacing the current suspension setup, we were able to optimise the double wishbone suspension setup in this project design. The sportfisherman bike has a single spring damping unit coupled with a double wishbone suspension setup that is connected to an upper and lower yoke. The subsequent sections provide a brief description of this suspension setup assembly and its optimisation method. With the help of this revolutionary setup, excellent caster and camber adjustment, optimal suspension setup weight, regulated tyre wear and tear, wheels in contact with the road, improved running and the ability to handle both vertical and lateral loads are all achieved.

These factors will be checked before the optimization of design and the results will be in decrease of weight. Autodesk fusion 360 is used for modelling and bluffing the double wishbone suspension figure.

Key words: Two-wheeler vehicle, Stability, Handling, Rider comfort, Adaptive damping.

1. INTRODUCTION

The double wishbone suspension setup, also known as an A-arm suspension, is a sophisticated mechanism employed in two-wheeler vehicles to enhance stability, handling, and overall performance. Unlike simpler suspension setups like the telescopic fork, the double wishbone setup consists of two separate control arms, usually shaped like the letter "A," connected to the wheel hub and the chassis at multiple points. This design allows for independent control of wheel movement, providing greater flexibility in optimizing both ride comfort and handling precision. By decoupling vertical and lateral forces, the double wishbone suspension effectively minimizes body roll during cornering while maintaining tire contact with the road surface, ensuring optimal traction and grip. Its modular structure also facilitates fine-tuning of suspension characteristics, catering to

various riding conditions and preferences. Though more complex and costly to manufacture compared to conventional setups, the double wishbone suspension remains a popular choice among high-performance two-wheeler enthusiasts and manufacturers striving for superior ride dynamics and control.

Figure 1: - Double Wishbone Suspension Setup

2. OBJECTIVES

Enhanced Stability: By independently controlling each wheel's movement, the double wishbone suspension setup helps stabilize the vehicle during acceleration, braking, and cornering. This stability is crucial for maintaining control and reducing the risk of accidents, especially at high speeds or on uneven road surfaces.

Improved Handling: The design of the double wishbone suspension allows for precise control over the vehicle's geometry, optimizing tire contact with the road surface. This results in improved handling characteristics, including better responsiveness to steering inputs, reduced body roll during cornering, and enhanced overall agility, making the vehicle more enjoyable to ride and easier to control.

Consistent Traction: Maximizing tire contact with the road is essential for ensuring consistent traction and grip, particularly during acceleration, braking, and cornering maneuvers. The double wishbone suspension setup helps distribute forces evenly across the tires, minimizing wheel hop and improving traction under various driving conditions, thereby enhancing both performance and safety.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Vignesh B S, Sufiyan Ahmed, Chandan V, Prashant Kumar Shrivastava, Double Wishbone Suspension Setup; A Research, International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE), ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-2, July 2019.

Faisal O. Mahroogi & S. Narayan, Design and Analysis of Double Wishbone Suspension Setups for Automotive Applications, Vol. 9, Issue 4, Aug 2019, International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development (IJMPERD).

Shubham Kadu, Kailas Gaware, Tushar Kale, Harshal. D. Patil, Study and Design of Advance Suspension Setup for Two-Wheeler, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395-0056 Volume: 05 Issue: 08 Aug 2018.

Akshay Bhoraskar, Ankur Fartyal, Analysis of the Double Wishbone Front Suspension Setup, International Conference on Nascent Technologies in the Engineering Field (ICNTE-2017).

4. MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

The materials and methodology employed in the construction of a double wishbone suspension setup for a two-wheeler vehicle are critical for achieving optimal performance, durability, and safety. Typically, lightweight yet sturdy materials such as aluminium alloys or high-strength steel are chosen for the construction of the control arms, ensuring a balance between strength and weight savings. The methodology involves precise engineering and manufacturing processes to design and fabricate the components with tight tolerances and minimal weight. Advanced techniques such as computer-aided design (CAD) and finite element analysis (FEA) are utilized to optimize the geometry and structural integrity of the components. Additionally, the selection of high-quality bearings, bushings, and damping elements plays a crucial role in ensuring smooth operation and longevity of the suspension setup. Rigorous testing, including simulations, laboratory experiments, and real-world evaluations, is conducted to validate the performance, reliability, and safety of the double wishbone suspension setup under various operating conditions. Overall, the materials and methodology employed in the design and construction of the double wishbone suspension setup are meticulously chosen and executed to achieve the desired balance of performance, durability, and safety in two-wheeler vehicles.

Figure 2: - Schematic view of Double Wishbone Suspension Setup

5. CONSTRUCTION AND WORKING MECHANISM

5.1. Construction:

The construction of a double wishbone suspension setup in a two-wheeler vehicle involves several key components and a precise arrangement of parts to achieve its working mechanism. Typically, the setup consists of two control arms (wishbones) for each wheel, connected to the wheel hub and the vehicle's frame or chassis.

1) Control Arms (Wishbones): The primary components of the double wishbone suspension setup are the upper and lower control arms. These arms are usually shaped like the letter "A" and are positioned parallel to each other.

2) Wheel Hub Assembly: The wheel hub assembly connects the control arms to the wheel, allowing for rotation and movement. It houses the wheel bearings, which enable smooth rotation of the wheel.

3) Spring and Damper Assembly: In most double wishbone suspension setups, a coil spring is used to support the weight of the vehicle and absorb shocks from the road surface. A damper (shock absorber) is often integrated with the spring to control the oscillations of the suspension setup and regulate its movement.

4) Ball Joints and Bushings: Ball joints are used to connect the control arms to the wheel hub assembly and allow for articulation and movement in multiple directions. Bushings are also employed at various points to provide cushioning and reduce friction between moving components.

5.2. Working Mechanism:

The double wishbone suspension setup allows each wheel to move independently, minimizing force transfer between sides. When encountering bumps, the spring and damper assembly absorbs vertical movement, while control arms pivot to maintain camber angle and wheel alignment. This geometry optimizes handling, stability, ride comfort, traction, and overall performance, surpassing simpler suspension designs.

Overall, the construction and working mechanism of the double wishbone suspension setup in a two-wheeler vehicle allow for independent wheel movement, precise control over suspension geometry, and effective damping of road disturbances, resulting in a smoother, more stable, and responsive ride.

Figure 3: - Schematic of Double Wishbone Suspension Setup

6. COMPONENTS

- UPPER CONTROL ARM
- LOWER CONTROL ARM
- WHEEL HUB ASSEMBLY

- SPRING
- DAMPER (SHOCK ABSORBER)
- BALL JOINTS
- BUSHINGS

6.1 UPPER CONTROL ARM

In a two-wheeler's double wishbone suspension, the upper control arm manages vertical wheel movement, connecting the wheel hub assembly to the vehicle's frame near the top. Its "A" shape and parallel alignment with the lower control arm enable it to transmit forces, controlling wheel movement while minimizing changes in alignment and camber angle. During road disturbances, the arm pivots around its mountings, allowing vertical wheel motion to absorb shocks and maintain tire contact with the ground for stability and traction. Overall, the upper control arm ensures smooth rides, stable handling, and consistent performance on diverse road surfaces.

6.2 LOWER CONTROL ARM

In a two-wheeler's double wishbone suspension, the lower control arm manages vertical wheel movement, connecting the wheel hub assembly to the vehicle's frame near the bottom. Its "A" shape and parallel alignment with the upper control arm enable it to regulate wheel movement, ensuring optimal tire contact with the road. During bumps or uneven terrain, the lower control

arm pivots around its mountings, allowing vertical wheel motion while minimizing changes in alignment and camber angle. By absorbing shocks and maintaining tire contact, it enhances stability, contributing to a smooth ride and reliable performance on different road surfaces.

6.3 WHEEL HUB ASSEMBLY

In a two-wheeler's double wishbone suspension, the wheel hub assembly connects the control arms to the wheel, housing the wheel bearings for smooth rotation. Positioned between the control arms, it distributes forces, supports the vehicle's weight, and ensures stability and alignment. By efficiently transmitting forces from the suspension setup to the wheel, the wheel hub assembly enhances traction and handling, playing a pivotal role in optimizing performance and stability on diverse road surfaces.

6.4 SPRING

In a two-wheeler vehicle's double wishbone suspension setup, the spring serves as a critical component for supporting the vehicle's weight and absorbing shocks from the road surface. Typically, a coil spring is utilized to provide the necessary compression resistance, allowing the suspension to maintain proper ride height and respond to varying road conditions. Positioned

between the control arms and the vehicle's frame or chassis, the spring absorbs vertical forces encountered during normal operation, ensuring a smooth and controlled ride experience. By effectively distributing the weight and energy from road disturbances, the spring contributes to enhanced stability, comfort, and handling, making it an essential element of the double wishbone suspension setup in two-wheeler vehicles.

6.5 DAMPER (SHOCK ABSORBER)

In a two-wheeler vehicle's double wishbone suspension setup, the damper, commonly known as the shock absorber, plays a vital role in controlling the oscillations of the suspension and regulating its movement. Integrated with the spring assembly, the damper dampens the rebound and compression motions generated by road irregularities, such as bumps and potholes. By absorbing and dissipating kinetic energy, the damper enhances ride comfort, stability, and handling. Positioned between the control arms and the vehicle's frame or chassis, it ensures that the suspension setup responds smoothly to changes in road surface, minimizing body roll and maintaining tire contact with the ground for optimal traction. Overall, the damper is essential for providing a balanced and controlled ride experience in two-wheeler vehicles equipped with double wishbone suspension.

6.6 BALL JOINTS

In a two-wheeler's double wishbone suspension setup, ball joints connect control arms to the wheel hub, enabling movement in various directions. They transmit forces, ensuring the setup effectively manages vertical movement for stability and alignment. Positioned strategically, ball joints maintain tire contact with the road, enhancing handling and traction. Their flexibility and articulation contribute to the setup's performance and reliability.

6.7 BUSHINGS

In a two-wheeler's double wishbone suspension, bushings are vital for cushioning and reducing friction between moving parts. They absorb vibrations, dampen shocks, and minimize friction, ensuring a smoother ride and responsive handling. Positioned throughout the setup, bushings maintain alignment and geometry, enhancing stability and tire longevity. In summary, bushings are crucial for improving ride quality, handling, and durability in two-wheeler vehicles with double wishbone suspension.

7.0 FABRICATION IMAGE

8.0 CALCULATIONS

- Weight distributed on rear axle is about 60% Maximum acceleration of bike can be 7m/s
- Weight of motorcycle = 190kg
- Weight of passenger = 80+80 = 160kg
- Longitudinal force = $m \times a = (190+160) \times 7 = 1750N$
- Maximum inclination angle about 40 degrees at 50km/hr.
- Maximum force = $(70/100) * m/g = 0.7 * 350 * 9.81 = 2,403.45N$
- Minimum force = $(30/100) * m/g = 0.3 * 350 * 9.81 = 1,030.05N$
- Braking condition = Max deceleration is -7m/s (at 50 to 0 in 2.9sec),
maximum force = $m * a = 350 * 7 = 2450N$

9.0 FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope for the double wishbone suspension setup in two-wheeler vehicles holds several promising avenues for improvement and innovation:

Advanced Materials: Continued research into lightweight yet durable materials, such as carbon fiber composites and advanced alloys, could lead to the development of even lighter and stronger components for the double wishbone suspension setup. This would not only reduce overall vehicle weight but also enhance performance and efficiency.

Smart Suspension Technology: Integration of smart sensors, actuators, and adaptive control setups could enable the double wishbone suspension to dynamically adjust damping rates, ride height, and stiffness in real-time based on road conditions, vehicle speed, and rider preferences. This would enhance ride comfort, stability, and handling across a wide range of driving scenarios.

Energy Harvesting: Incorporating energy harvesting technologies, such as regenerative shock absorbers or piezoelectric materials, into the double wishbone suspension setup could capture and convert kinetic energy from road disturbances into electrical energy. This harvested energy could then be used to power auxiliary setups or recharge onboard batteries, improving overall energy efficiency and reducing fuel consumption.

Active Aero Dynamics: Integration of active aerodynamic features, such as adjustable winglets or fairings, into the double wishbone suspension setup could optimize airflow around the vehicle, reducing aerodynamic drag and enhancing stability at high speeds. This would improve fuel efficiency and performance while reducing wind noise and rider fatigue.

Modular Design: Designing the double wishbone suspension setup with modular components and interfaces would allow for easier customization and integration of aftermarket upgrades or accessories, providing riders with greater flexibility to tailor their vehicle's suspension characteristics to their specific preferences and riding style.

Autonomous Riding: With the advent of autonomous vehicle technology, the double wishbone suspension setup could be integrated with advanced driver assistance setups (ADAS) and autonomous riding features to enhance vehicle stability, safety, and comfort during self-driving operation. This could include features such as predictive suspension adjustment based on road conditions or autonomous collision avoidance maneuvers.

In order to significantly enhance performance, economy, and rider experience, the double wishbone suspension system in two-wheeled vehicles will likely continue to progress due to advancements in technology, materials, and design principles.

CONCLUSION

We can achieve the necessary caster, camber, and ground clearance by using a double wishbone suspension system. Thus, we may rank this as the greatest suspension system suitable for most Formula Cars and Bikes. The expansion of the negative chamber resulting from the vertical suspension movement of the upper and lower arms is one of the main advantages of the double wishbone suspension system. Thus, handling performance also improves as a result. Material selection is another important factor for designing a vehicle as this is the department where we can increase the performance of the vehicle by reducing its weight while keeping in mind the safety of the designed components.

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